

```
public class DiscountCalculator {

    public double calculatePrice(double price, int quantity, boolean isMember) {
        if (price < 0 || quantity < 0) {
            return -1.0;
        }

        double total = price * quantity;

        if (quantity >= 10) {
            total = total * 0.90;
        }

        if (isMember) {
            total = total - 5.0;
        }

        if (total < 0) {
            total = 0;
        }

        return total;
    }

    public static void main(String[] args) {
        DiscountCalculator calc = new DiscountCalculator();
        System.out.println("Result 1: " + calc.calculatePrice(10.0, 5, false));
        System.out.println("Result 2: " + calc.calculatePrice(10.0, 15, false));
        System.out.println("Result 3: " + calc.calculatePrice(10.0, 5, true));
    }
}
```